

Application of the magnetic tracer-tracking system in solids circulation measurement in a fluidized bed standpipe

Chunguang Zhou^{a,b,*}, Christian Jonasson^c, Marcus Gullberg^d, Fredrik Ahrentorp^c, Christer Johansson^c

^a Department of Chemical Engineering, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Teknikringen 42, SE-10044 Stockholm, Sweden

^b Phoenix Biopower AB, Drottning Kristinas väg 18, 114 28 Stockholm, Sweden

^c Department of Smart Hardware, RISE Research Institutes of Sweden, Göteborg, Sweden

^d Department of Biorefinery and Energy, RISE Research Institutes of Sweden, Piteå, Sweden

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ABSTRACT

In the present study, the application of a magnetic tracer-tracking method in measuring solids circulation in a fluidized bed standpipe is investigated, due to its advantages of little intervention and cost efficiency, especially in pressurized systems. The method only needs to inject one small magnetic tracer to follow the main solid flow in the standpipe, therefore predicting particles' real-time velocities. The measurement accuracy was thoroughly tested via comparing to conventional descending and accumulation methods. Main tracer properties, including tracer shape, density, and magnet core, were considered. Solids flow patterns in the standpipe were also regulated by changing orifice sizes and adding an inclined pipe, for the purpose of investigating the measurement accuracy in various conditions. The adverse effect of a narrow orifice on measurement was addressed via constructing a model that includes sand particles' non-uniform velocity distribution across the standpipe cross-section. To interpret behaviors of tracers varied in size and density, a mathematical model was constructed to describe forces exerted on the tracer in the solids bed. The behaviors of the tracer immersed into the solids bed were also examined, providing an insight to that in a standpipe with continuous solids circulation. The solids bed density was also regulated by varying the mixture of olivine sand and carbonaceous particles at different proportions. The magnetic tracer-tracking method has been successfully validated, demonstrating good measurement accuracy of solids discharge flow rates in the standpipe, particularly avoiding cumbersome calibration. Moreover, the method can also determine sand waving and oscillated discharge behaviors, which might be related to solids' stick-slip phenomena and is unlikely to be accurately determined using conventional descending and accumulation methods.

1. Introduction

Solids circulation is a key characteristic of circulating fluidized beds, in which circulating particles, driven by a high-velocity fluidization gas flow, are generally transferred to the top of a fluidized bed, separated from the gas flow in a cyclone, collected and returned in a standpipe to the bottom of the fluidized bed, forming a closed solids loop. The solids can act as a heat transfer medium in fluidized beds and as a catalyst or reactant participating in reactions in processes, therefore their travel, concentration, and distribution affect both heat and mass transport and determine the gas–solid contact time and the performance of fluidized bed reactors [1]. Consequently, the circulation rate of these solids is

important for controlling reactions in conversion processes, e.g. biomass gasification rates in gasifiers [2]. Depending on types of fluidized bed reactors and design targets, the circulation rate varies in a wide range from 2.5 to 3400 kg/m² s [2]. Thus, an accurate online measurement of solids circulation behaviors is very important to quantify the effect of operating and design parameters on the performance of circulating fluidized beds.

Many measuring technologies have been introduced to measure solids flux profiles in the riser. Operating parameters like pressure drop, which is easy to obtain, were correlated to the solids flux [3–5]. Patience et al. [6] tried to correlate the solids mass flux with the measured gas velocity and pressure drop in the horizontal section between the riser

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: chunguan@kth.se (C. Zhou).

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and cyclone of a CFB. Monzam et al. [5] also developed a method to estimate the solids flow rate based on the pressure drop over the horizontal section. Several correlations were formulated as a function of the pressure drop, however, some of coefficients found in these correlations were quite dependent on the operating conditions. Moreover, the particular design of the probe also introduces limitations to the measurement and changes to the flow pattern [6]. Momentum probes and particles sampling probes have been used to extract solids locally to measure local momentum fluxes of gas-solid flow and particles fluxes within the CFB [7–10]. The solids mass flux can also be deduced from measurement results of local distributions of solids concentrations as well as local solids velocities in a CFB using fiber optic probes [7,11,12]. However, to obtain the total mass flux, a detailed picture of the flow structure over the bed's cross-sectional area of the circulating fluidized bed is needed due to inhomogeneous solids distributions in the core and annular zones of the riser, with a dilute rising core and a dense descending annular region close to the wall [7]. The local time-average solid mass flux can vary with axial and radial positions, elevation, total solids mass flow, superficial gas velocity, and mean particle diameter [8,9]. Therefore, a series of measuring points in a cross-section for fiber-optic probes is needed to fit and validate the mathematical form of velocity and particle concentration fields, which calculates the total circulation rate by the integral of the product of concentration multiplied by the corresponding velocity in the cross section [13,14]. The main factor constraining the optical method's application is that it only captures flow in a plane and is not suitable for the complicated gas–solid flow measurement in large scale equipment [3]. Some novel methods based on specific instruments have also been applied to measure solids flow patterns in a riser [6,15–17]. Radar technology was applied to measure concentrations and velocity distributions of the solid particles along the height of a riser, to investigate solids back-mixing behaviors in the freeboard of a circulating fluidized bed [18]. Jaworski and Dyakowski [15] used an electrical capacitance tomography (ECT) to investigate the complexities of flow morphology in a dense pneumatic conveying system. The technique underestimated the solids mass flow rate typically by 20–30 % and required complicated calibration, e.g. additional estimation of solids velocity, implying comparatively higher cost of implementations [6]. Moreover, all these methods need to be calibrated by estimating the solids mass flux independently from tests designed by the time-of-descent method [11].

An alternative way is to measure the solids flow in the standpipe rather than local mass fluxes in the riser. One of the most common methods is the accumulation method, which records the accumulated solids mass and accumulation time in a downcomer after shutting off a valve in a standpipe or bypassing the down-flowing solids in the standpipe into a container [6,19,20]. However, the method modifies the total inventory and might change the pressure balance in the whole loop, disturbing normal solids circulation [21]. Therefore, the ratio of the accumulated mass to the total inventory should be small enough to mitigate the disturbance caused by the change of bed inventory. The circulation rate can also be measured by tracking the change in height of accumulated bed rather than weighing the mass of accumulated sand [22]. However, this method still cannot overcome the inherent shortcoming—closing a part of transfer pipe is bound to upset the pressure balance and thereby affects the circulation rate measurement [22]. Moreover, this visual determination technique needs a transparent wall or sight glasses windows for visual observation.

Some flow meters and devices have also been developed and installed in the standpipe to measure the bulk solids flow rate. Burkell et al. [11] considered five different methods of measuring solids circulation rates in a vertical standpipe with a diameter much larger than that of the riser for solids accumulation. A butterfly valve with two diametrically opposed semicircular aluminum plates drilled with holes and covered with a mesh screen was used in the middle of the vertical standpipe as a permeable valve to accumulate solids. The accumulation lasted around 30 s and was determined by monitoring the rate of the

change of pressure drop over the valve. At least 10 min was needed to re-establish steady gas and solids flowrates throughout the loop between successive measurements. However, it can cause interferences, especially for systems with a L-valve return loop and a large inventory of solids [11]. Burkell et al. [11] modified an orifice meter and concluded that it is not well suited for measuring circulation of circulating fluidized beds due to the countercurrent gas/solids motion in the return line. An impact flowmeter was also designed and tested to measure the force of solids falling onto an inverted-V-shaped “pan” suspended across the column in the standpipe. Pulse signals were obtained and attributed to periodic build-up and dumping of solids from inclined surfaces of the pan, non-uniform processing sheets of solids from the cyclone, and the turbulence in the riser section. The amplitude of the force fluctuations increased dramatically with an increase of solids circulation. The application of the impact flowmeter is limited due to time-variations in force signals [11]. Impact flow meters determine the impact force or torque that acts on a hinged plate installed in the standpipe [23,24]. The signal generated by the force of collision can be acquired for further analysis. The signal can be either correlated with particles momentum, or the solids circulation rate [3,25]. Methods with similar principles have also been reported. Liu and Hunan [26] developed a bulk solids flow rate turbine meter (BSFTM), which used the rotation rate of turbine to measure bulk solids volumetric flowrate when the solids went down in plug flow. The influence of the turbine geometry and solids materials measured should be considered and tested. A rotating Spiral vane, which rotates as a consequence of the motion of solids flow, was used to continuously measure solids circulation rates [27]. However, a set of statistically-designed experiments was needed to correct the solids velocity and solids fraction in the standpipe as a function of aeration rate in the standpipe [27–29]. The fourth method applied by Burkell et al. [11] is based on a simple heat balance when high temperature solids flow downward in a standpipe through a jacketed cooling section. The method is very sensitive to the radial position due to temperature gradients in the descending solids [11,21]. All these methods need to be calibrated in case of the change of applied circumstances. The fifth technique was based on the time-of-descent concept and used colored alumina or sand particles at 5 different circumferential positions around a L-valve to descend through a 0.3 m vertical distance in a transparent section of the vertical standpipe [11]. Compared to the other four methods, the time-of-descent measurement is reasonably accurate and reliable [11]. However, this method is limited in a large 3D since colored particles immersed in the bulk solids flow are difficult to visually observe from quartz windows.

To overcome the limitations of visual observation, different tracers have been applied into the gas–solid flow for the circulation rate measurement via determining the tracer's moving velocity and assuming the tracer has the same velocity as the bulk solids flow. Fluorescent tracer particles are commonly used and their movement can be detected using optical fiber probes or cameras [30,31]. The tracer can be hidden by other bed materials therefore this method is generally limited to a quasi-2D flow section and not suitable for the case in the standpipe [3,32]. Solids velocity and volume fraction distribution were measured by tracking a single radioactive particle as tracer and γ -ray densitometry, respectively [1]. The deviation of mass flux values from those obtained from a timing and weighing method was within 4 % [1]. Although radioactive methods have been demonstrated and are readily applicable, they are expensive, implying potential health risks and therefore demanding extraordinary safety measures [33,34]. Guío-Pérez et al. [6,35] measured the solids circulation rate in a circulating fluidized bed cold model by injecting about 0.05 % by mass fluid-dynamically μ -sized ferromagnetic particles, and the concentration of particles was detected by measuring the change in inductance of a coil when the particles passing through it. In this method a collection system consisting of an arrangement of permanent magnets is needed to attract the passing ferromagnetic particles during the collection stage and inject collected particles pneumatically during the injection stage [6].

However, the method does not directly measure the velocity of tracer and solids particles, but widely adopted for investigating particles mixing and dispersion in fluidized bed systems.

The measurement of solids circulation is more challenging in pressurized systems since the measurement devices need to be able to withstand the high operating pressure and a thick pressure vessel can also be a big obstacle for designing a reliable interface for measurement probes, e.g. optical fibre probe, which in consequence significantly increases the development cost to adapt conventional methods in pressurized systems. Compared with a conventional atmospheric fluidized bed, the elevation of pressure can increase the gas density, promotes gas-particle interaction, and influence the gas–solid flow characteristics [36]. In-depth understanding of the fluidization performance is essential for the design, optimization, and scale-up of fluidized beds.

In this study, the magnetic tracer-tracking method will be first applied in measuring solids movement and discharge flow rates in a fluidized bed standpipe. The magnetic-tracer-tracking method has been used in previous studies on bubbling fluidized beds, yielding quantitative information applicable to the study of fuel mixing in large-scale fluidized bed processes, overcoming the limitation in signal penetration which prevents tracking of radioactive objects in such dense media [37–39]. Only a single small magnetic tracer (a NdFeB-based magnet) is injected and by reading the magnetic stray fields from the tracer using magnetic sensors, it is possible to follow the main solids flow for each measurement. Therefore, it does not affect the solids flow in the system and can be considered as a non-invasive method. A full-loop fluidized bed system consists of a riser, where particle mixing and reactions occur, and a standpipe, where entrained particles are collected and returned to the riser. In the fluidized bed riser, the dense bed in the bottom is in bubbling/turbulent fluidization regimes. Due to the existence of bubbles and dissimilar fuel and bed particles, there is significant randomness in the movement of a single particle and inhomogeneity in particle hydrodynamics. It is unlikely that the trajectories of an individual tracer particle are adequate to represent the moving status of the whole bed. While in the standpipe, the solids flow in the standpipe is generally in the moving packed-bed regime. Particles in the moving packed bed, which are mainly driven by gravity and pressure gradient over the bed, have a high similarity in the movement in the axial direction of the standpipe. Although the size of the tracer might differ from the sand particles in the standpipe, its movement in the moving packed bed is confined by neighboring sand particles, with the gravity force balanced by the forces originated from the interactions with neighboring sand particles rather than gas bubbles. Therefore, it is expected that both the tracer and sand particles exhibit a similar moving velocity in the axial direction for a moving packed-bed flow in the standpipe. Tracing individual tracer particles can help determine the bed moving velocity in the axial direction and elucidate solids discharge behaviors in the standpipe. However, its measurement accuracy in predicting solids flow is still unknown due to the lack of knowledge of interactions between the tracer and moving bulk-flow particles. Although it is unlikely that the single tracer affects the main gas–solid flow state, its movement can be strongly influenced by the gas–solid flow. Therefore, the accuracy of interpreting its tracking trajectory as a good representative of the main solid flow has not been studied in detail before. Moreover, there exist some parameters (e.g. tracer size, density, and solid flow pattern inside the standpipe) that might affect the measurement accuracy and need to be optimized. Granular materials tend to segregate when particles in the mixture differ in density [40]. The phenomenon can be observed in a variety of natural and industrial processes, e.g. deposits of dense geophysical flows [41], vibrofluidized beds [42], gravity-driven flows in rotating drums [43], and down-inclined planes [44]. Thus, this study investigated the accuracy of the magnetic tracer-tracking method in measuring solids discharge in a fluidized bed standpipe under various conditions (i.e. different orifice sizes, tracer properties, immersed depth in the bed) via comparing the results with that obtained using descending and accumulation methods. The method was then applied in

a solids-return unit consisting of a vertical standpipe and an inclined pipe, which was constructed for returning solids in a pressurized fluidized bed system. Considering that the density of the bed in the standpipe could vary with the amount of entrained char particles in a hot fluidized bed system, e.g. gasifier, tests with both sand and biomass particles at different proportions in the standpipe were also conducted. The validated magnetic tracer-tracking method can be used to predict solids behaviors that cannot be unveiled using conventional descending and accumulation methods. Moreover, the magnetic tracer-tracking method has a high potential of the circulation measurement in a system at elevated temperatures, via selecting suitable magnetic materials with a high working temperature of the tracers. For example, NdFeB based magnets have a highest working temperature of up to about 250 °C while SmCo based magnets have higher working temperatures in the range of up to 550 °C [45–47]. Moreover, since the tracer sensing system (magnetic sensor nodes) is installed outside the pressure vessel to track the tracer, this method can also be easily applied for measuring solids circulation in a pressurized fluidized bed system.

2. Methodology

2.1. Magnetic tracer-tracking system

The magnetic tracer-tracking system consists of a number of magnetic field sensors (magnetic sensor nodes) that read the magnetic field in three-dimensions from the magnetic tracer element (e.g. NdFeB-based permanent magnet) [37]. The magnetic stray field from the magnetic tracer can be considered as the field from a magnetic dipole with a magnetic moment, μ_m . From the readings of the surrounding magnetic sensor nodes and using optimization fitting algorithms, the time dependent positions, x , y and z , and orientations, θ , φ , of the magnetic moment of the tracer can be determined, see Fig. 1.

One advantage of the magnetic tracer-tracking system is that no clear optical line of sight is needed between the sensors and magnetic tracer to be measured, as long as the standpipe-material is not made of any magnetic material that shields the stray fields from the magnetic tracer or distorts the magnetic fields at the magnetic sensors. Not only the time evaluation of the tracer position (that gives the flow velocity) but also the orientation of the tracer can be determined. The tracer orientation

Fig. 1. Schematic image of the magnetic tracer with a magnetic moment, μ_m , located at position x , y , z and oriented with angles θ , φ with respect to the coordinate system. The sensor nodes read the magnetic stray field from the magnetic tracer that depends on the position and orientation of the tracer with respect to the sensor node. For clarity in the figure, only one sensor node is shown. In the real system several sensor nodes surrounding the measuring volume were used. The z -axis is in the length direction of the standpipe.

gives valuable information of the flow in the standpipe. The magnetic tracers are made of a magnetic inner core of NdFeB-based cylindrical magnets symmetrically positioned in a spherical polymer shell (3D-printed) that builds up the tracer element. The polymer shell is made of PETG (Polyethylene Terephthalate with Glycol) and the NdFeB-based magnets are of grade N36 (4×4 mm cylinder) and N35 (3×3 mm cylinder) with a remanence magnetization of 1.2 T. Different sizes of the core magnets and outer shell diameters were used to vary the effective density of the tracer. The effective density of the tracer elements is determined by considering the total tracer mass (sum of magnet and polymer shell) divided with the total tracer volume. The bare magnetic tracer has a much larger diameter and larger particle density than the solids particles in the standpipe. However, via wrapping the tracer using a plastic casing with different sizes, the effective tracer density changes, therefore regulating fluid-dynamic similarity between the tracer and fluid materials. The bare magnetic tracer has a particle density of 7600 kg/m^3 . The tracer density can be lowered to the level of the bulk density of solids particles in the standpipe. The equivalent spherical diameters of 4×4 mm and 3×3 mm bare tracers are 4.6 mm and 3.4 mm, respectively. With the spherical polymer shell, the diameter of tracers increases to 6–7.5 mm, while the density decreases to 1000–2000 kg/m^3 .

The magnetic reading system consists of several sensor nodes including three-axis magnetometers from Honeywell (HMC 1053) and electronics for signal amplification, analog-to-digital converting and sampling. Also, on each sensor node there are electronics for sending the data to a main control module on a common RS485 bus. The control module communicates by User Datagram Protocol (UDP) to the Ethernet port on a PC that controls the measurement and stores the data. The magnetic tracer-tracking system has a spatial resolution of around 1 mm

and a time resolution of 10^{-3} s [39]. Considering the characteristic distance for evaluating particles dispersion is typically in the order of 0.01 m [38], the level of accuracy is high enough for the measurements in this study. The total data signal analysis decreases the effective sample rate to 100 Hz, meaning that the system delivers $x(t)$, $y(t)$, $z(t)$, $\theta(t)$ and $\varphi(t)$ data every 10 ms.

2.2. Experimental section

2.2.1. Experimental apparatus

A pilot-scale pressurized fluidized bed system was constructed at RISE, Piteå, for hydrodynamics tests under pressurized conditions. The schematic diagram of the system consists of a riser, a cyclone, a standpipe, and an inclined pipe, as illustrated in Fig. 2(a). The part with the standpipe and inclined pipe was used for testing in this study, as shown in Fig. 2(b). The standpipe was made of Plexiglas pipe and installed in a stainless pressure vessel equipped with glass windows at different levels for visual observation of solids movement in the transparent Plexiglas standpipe. A series of magnetic sensor nodes were installed at two different level heights surrounding the pressure vessel of the standpipe, as shown in Fig. 2(c). Fig. 2(d) shows coordinate axes of the magnetic tracer tracking system in the sensing zone. There are four sensor nodes installed at each level. The associate angles of the tracer are illustrated in Fig. 1.

In this study, the bed return part including the standpipe and the inclined pipe were used for testing and validating the magnetic tracer-tracking method. Tests were performed with two different rig configurations: standpipe, standpipe & inclined, with their schematic diagrams as shown in Fig. 2(e) and (f), respectively. The Plexiglas pipe in the

Fig. 2. Pilot-scale pressurized fluidized bed system at RISE, Piteå: (a) pressurized fluidized bed system with installed magnetic tracer-tracking system, including riser (1), cyclone (2), vertical standpipe (3), inclined pipe (4), glass windows (5), pressure vessel wall (6), plexiglas (7), magnetic tracer sensing zone (8), magnetic tracer-tracking sensors (9); (b) testing system used in this study; (c) vertical standpipe with glass windows and installed magnetic sensors; (d) coordinate axes of the magnetic tracer tracking system in the sensing zone; (e) schematic diagram of testing facility with only vertical standpipe; (f) schematic diagram of testing facility with both vertical standpipe and inclined pipe.

vertical standpipe and the inclined pipe have the same inner diameter of 123 mm but different pipe lengths of around 5 m and 0.8 m, respectively. The angle between the center axes of vertical standpipe and inclined pipe is 37.5°. The magnetic tracer-tracking method was validated via comparing the results obtained from the conventional descending (observed from glass windows in Fig. 2(c)) and accumulation methods (measured using a solids bucket and a weighing scale in Fig. 2(e) and (f)).

2.2.2. Materials

Olivine sand, supplied by SIBELCO, was used as solids materials in the standpipe during the tests. The particle size distribution is illustrated in Fig. 3. The materials properties are shown in Table 1 below.

As shown in Table 1, the olivine sand contains Fe₂O₃, that exists in the alpha phase (hematite) which has very low magnetic properties. The magnetic characteristics of the olivine sand were tested before using as solids in the fluidized bed standpipe. The test confirmed that the selected olivine sand has a very low magnetic response and is suitable to be used together with the magnetic tracer, and therefore exhibiting no effect on the detection performance of the magnetic tracer in a lab sensing system similar to that adopted in Fig. 2(c) and (d).

2.2.3. Operating conditions and procedures

Table 2 shows the experimental testing cases and operating conditions. In tests using only vertical standpipe (Fig. 2(e)) for solids discharge, an orifice was directly installed at the bottom of the standpipe to regulate the solids discharge flow. After blocking the orifice using a blind plate, a given amount of bed materials was loaded to the Plexiglas standpipe. A background test was first conducted to measure the background magnetic signals, which then was removed from the following tracer measurement signal in the post-processing of sensor data series. A tracer was then fed by gravity from the top of the cyclone (Fig. 2(e)) into the bed. The measurement of the magnetic tracer-tracking started prior to withdrawing the bottom blind plate for solids discharge. A solids bucket loaded on a weighing scale was used to collect the solids discharged from the standpipe and measure the accumulated mass continuously, which is the main measure to validate the magnetic tracer-tracking measurement method. Test C#1 was performed with a magnetic tracer on the bed surface and repeated three times to check the repeatability of measurement results. Test C#2 was conducted under conditions same as test C#1, but with a camera at the glass windows on the side of the standpipe to measure the descending speed of the bed surface level, as a comparison of the magnetic tracer-tracking method. The effect of orifice sizes (41 mm, 90 mm, and full opening) on the solids discharge flow rate and the magnetic tracer-tracking measurement was investigated via comparing tests C#1, C#3, and C#4. A 3 × 3 mm

Table 1

Bed materials properties.

Components	wt. %
MgO	50.0
SiO ₂ ^a	41.6
Fe ₂ O ₃	7.4
Al ₂ O ₃	0.41
Cr ₂ O ₃	0.29
NiO	0.32
MnO	0.09
L.O.L. ^b	0.6

^a Present as silicate, contains < 0.1 % free crystalline silica.

^b Weight reduction after 30 min at 900C/air.

cylindrical bare tracer and spherical tracers with different magnetic cores (4 × 4 mm, 3 × 3 mm) and sizes of 6 mm, 7 mm, and 7.5 mm were also used, as illustrated by tests C#4, C#5, C#6, and C#7. In tests C#8 and C#9, three tracers were immersed at different depths in the bed, to investigate the effect of in-bed depth on tracer behaviors in the bed. The three tracers were fed separately in sequence with 20 kg solids loaded between neighboring tracers to keep tracers far apart from each other, avoiding mutual interference during measurement. The in-bed depths of the 1st, 2nd, and 3rd tracers are around 1.9 m, 0.95 m, and 0 m (bed surface), respectively.

Tests from C#10 to C#19 were performed on the rig configuration with both the standpipe and inclined pipe (Fig. 2(f)). Besides the variants (i.e. orifice size, in-bed depth) mentioned above, the bed density was considered in the test matrix. The bed density was regulated in the range of 480 kg/m³ to 1780 kg/m³ by mixing olivine bed and wood particles at different proportions, with the purpose of simulating the solids mixture of solids sand and biochar particles in a hot standpipe. 2 to 3 tracers were used and fed to the standpipe in sequence in tests from C#15 to C#18, with 10 l solids loaded between neighboring tracers.

2.2.4. Calculation of tracer velocity and solids mass flow rate in the standpipe

Moving average velocities of the tracer particle every (interval times) 50 ms, 150 ms, and 300 ms through the whole data series were calculated and compared. The sampling frequency is 100 Hz meaning 10 ms between adjacent data points. The probability density function of the velocities obtained with different interval times was plotted and presented in Fig. S1(a) and (b) in the Supporting Information. The peak height of curves changes when changing the interval time, since the moving average velocities can shift to the peak value with increasing the interval time. However, the change of the peak value is not obvious with further increasing the interval time from 150 ms to 300 ms. Moreover, average velocities with increasing interval times almost remain unchanged, as shown in Fig. S1(c). Therefore, the interval time of 150 ms (meaning a moving average of 15 velocity values) was adopted. For comparison reason, the moving average velocities of tests that were compared were calculated in the same zone (with the same starting and ending points in the length direction of the standpipe) in the tracer coordinate axes. The calculation was based on its position in x, y, and z directions in the sensing zone, and the mean velocity v_{ij} for sample index j is given by

$$v_{ij} = \frac{dp_{ij}}{dt_{ij}} = \frac{p_{ij-5} - p_{ij+10}}{0.15} \quad (1)$$

dp_{ij} is the change of particle position (p_{ij-5}, p_{ij+10}) in i direction (i.e. x, y, z) between the sample index $j+10$ and $j-5$. dt_{ij} is the time zone, e.g. 0.15 s in this study.

The average value \bar{v}_z of moving average velocities in z direction in selected zones can be calculated. The corresponding standard deviation σ is calculated, with the expression in Equation (2).

Fig. 3. Size distribution of used olivine sand.

Table 2
Experimental tests and operating conditions.

Cases	Inclined pipe	Orifice (mm)	Solids	Mass (kg)	Bed density (kg/m ³)	Tracer ^a (mm)	Core ^b (mm)	Tracer No.	In-bed depth (m)
C#1-1,C#1-2; C#1-3	No	90	Olivine	23.6	1780	7.5	4 × 4	1	0
C#2		90	Olivine	23.6	1780	–	–	–	–
C#3		No	Olivine	23.6	1780	7.5	4 × 4	1	0
C#4-1,C#4-2		41	Olivine	23.6	1780	7.5	4 × 4	1	0
C#5-1,C#5-2		41	Olivine	23.6	1780	6	3 × 3	1	0
C#6-1,C#6-2		41	Olivine	23.6	1780	7	3 × 3	1	0
C#7-1,C#7-2		41	Olivine	23.6	1780	bare ^c	3 × 3	1	0
C#8-1,C#8-2,C#8-3		41	Olivine	63	1780	7.5	4 × 4	3	1.9/0.95/0
C#9-1,C#9-2,C#9-3		90	Olivine	63	1780	7.5	4 × 4	3	1.9/0.95/0
C#10	Yes	41	Olivine	63.2	1780	7.5	4 × 4	2	0.95/0/0
C#11		90	Olivine	63.2	1780	7.5	4 × 4	2	0.95/0
C#12		No	Olivine	43.2	1780	7.5	4 × 4	1	0
C#13		90	Olivine, wood	10&10	800	7.5	4 × 4	1	0
C#14		No	Olivine, wood	10&10	800	7.5	4 × 4	1	0
C#15		90	Olivine, wood	20&10	984	7.5	4 × 4	2	0.85/0
C#16		No	Olivine, wood	20&10	984	7.5	4 × 4	2	0.85/0
C#17		90	Olivine, wood	40&10	1250	7.5	4 × 4	3	1.7/0.85/0
C#18		No	Olivine, wood	40&10	1250	7.5	4 × 4	2	0.85/0
C#19		No	wood	14.4	480	7.5	4 × 4	1	0

^a Outer diameter of the spherical tracer.

^b Cylindrical magnetic core in the tracer.

^c Bare means a tracer with no casing.

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum (v_{z,j} - \bar{v}_z)^2}{n}} \quad (2)$$

where n is the number of moving average velocities in selected zones.

Moreover, the solids moving velocity in the standpipe can also be calculated, if more than one tracer far apart from each other was used in the measurement and the distance between neighboring tracers was known. The expression is as follows in Equation (3).

$$v_{g_{k,k+1}} = \frac{D_{k,k+1}}{t_{k+1,j} - t_{k,j}} \quad (3)$$

$D_{k,k+1}$ is the distance between two neighboring tracers ($k, k + 1$). For test with multiple tracers, a given amount of solids is loaded between neighboring tracers to ensure they are far apart from each other, avoiding mutual interference. The distance between the two tracers is calculated by dividing the solids mass between the tracers with the solid bulk density and the cross-section area of the standpipe. The depth of tracers in the sand bed in each test is shown in Table 2. $t_{k+1,j}$ and $t_{k,j}$ are the time of the tracers $k + 1$ and k passing through the bed level at $z = j$, respectively.

2.2.5. Other measurement methods

2.2.5.1. Descending method. The descending of the bed surface level in the standpipe was recorded using a camera at two side glass windows. The moving speed can be calculated by Equation (4).

$$v_s = \frac{L}{t_1 - t_2} \quad (4)$$

L is the known distance between the center points of two side glass windows in z direction. t_1 and t_2 are the time of the bed surface level passing through the center point of the first and the second glass windows, respectively.

2.2.5.2. Accumulation method. A weighing scale (full range 120 kg, measurement accuracy ± 30 g) was used to continuously measure the mass of accumulated bed particles in a bucket. The solids moving velocity in different time periods can therefore be calculated easily to validate the magnetic tracer-tracking method.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Measurement of solids movement in the vertical standpipe

3.1.1. Validation of tracer-tracking method using descending and accumulation methods

Fig. 4 shows the magnetic tracer movement and sand particles mass flow in the vertical standpipe with a 90 mm orifice installed at the exit. As shown in Fig. 4(a), the movement of the magnetic tracer was detected at around $z = 60$ cm in the coordinate axes and lasted around 7 s before disappearing from the lower detection limit of the sensing zone at around $z = -5$ cm. The tracer exhibits an expected change of position with time in the z direction, due to its sinking-down movement together with sand particles, with a good repeatability among tests C#1-1, C#1-2, and C#1-3. However, only slight changes can be observed from x and y directions, as presented in Fig. S2(a), (b), and (c) in the [Supporting Information](#). The moving average velocities of the tracer in x , y , and z directions were calculated and presented in Fig. 4(a) and Fig. S2. For all three repeated tests, the velocity in z direction fluctuates significantly in a wide range from 2 cm/s to 15 cm/s before $t = 6$ s, while the fluctuation turns out to be relatively small at the velocity of around 9 cm/s after $t = 6$ s. Two zones with different behaviors can therefore be observed and denoted as zone 1 and zone 2 in Fig. 4(a). The velocities in x and y directions also exhibit a similar fluctuation before descending to the bed level at around $z = 40$ cm in the coordinate axes, as shown in Fig. S2. Fig. 4(b) shows the probability density function of the tracer moving average velocities in the zone from $z = 48$ cm to $z = -5$ cm in z direction for the repeated tests of C#1-1, C#1-2, and C#-3. Although the profile of test C#1-3 slightly shifts to the right compared to C#1-1 and C#1-2, all the three profiles show a peak value around 9 cm/s and a similar peak width. The average velocities in the whole test zone (zone from $z = 48$ cm to $z = -5$ cm) and zone 2, as marked in Fig. 4(a), are presented in Fig. 4(c). A comparison among the three tests shows that a better repeatability can be achieved in zone 2, which is consistent with the finding observed in Fig. 4(a). In Fig. 4(c), the tracer average velocities in zone 2 in z direction are only slightly lower than that obtained by calculating the descending speed of bed surface at the side glass windows. With the obtained velocities, the solids discharge rates were calculated and compared with the corresponding mass flow rates of sand collected using a bucket loaded on a weighing scale, as shown in Fig. 2 (e) and Fig. 4(d). The comparison in Fig. 4(c) and 4(d) shows that the

Fig. 4. Magnetic tracer movement and sand mass flow in the vertical standpipe with a 90 mm orifice (a): C#1-1, C#1-2, C#1-3, tracer position and velocities in z direction, zone 1 ($z = 48$ cm to $z = 30$ cm) and zone 2 ($z = 30$ cm to $z = -5$ cm) as marked are based on velocity fluctuation; (b) probability density function of tracer moving average velocities in the zone (zone 1 and zone 2) descending from $z = 48$ cm to $z = -5$ cm in z direction; (c) comparison of tracer average velocities in z direction and the sand bed level moving-down velocity obtained via visual observation (bed-surface descending method); (d) comparison of sand mass flow rates measured using magnetic tracer-tracking and accumulation methods.

velocity and sand mass flow results calculated based on tracer trajectory are very similar to that measured using descending and accumulation methods, indicating a good measurement accuracy of the magnetic tracer-tracking method. It can be observed in Fig. 4(d) that the sand mass flow measured using the accumulation method in test C#1-3 is highest among the three repeated tests, which was also successfully determined by the tracer-tracking method, as shown in Fig. 4(b), where the profile in test C#1-3 slightly shifts to the right. The differences among the three repeated tests in Fig. 4(b) and 4(d) could be attributed to the deviation of the orifice center from the axis of the vertical standpipe, which can differ slightly when installing the orifice at the exit of the standpipe, consequently resulting in changes of the tracer moving average velocity and sand mass flow.

3.1.2. Effect of orifice size installed in the end of vertical standpipe

Fig. 5 shows measurement results of tracer and sand particles moving in the vertical standpipe with a 41 mm orifice installed at the exit of the standpipe. The tracer exhibits different position profiles in z direction in Fig. 5(a), compared to that in Fig. 4(a). An obvious change of line slope rate at around $z = 15$ cm can be observed in Fig. 5(a). A similar change at around $t = 18$ s could also be observed from the position profiles in x and y directions in Fig. S3. The significant change in line slope near $z = 15$ cm in Fig. 5(a) could be attributed to the change of the flow pattern of sand particles when approaching the narrow orifice exit, where a stagnant zone above the circular orifice near the standpipe wall and a funnel

flow in the center area could form. Moreover, a turning point at around $t = 10$ s can also be observed from the x and y position profiles. Thus, the whole measurement time is divided into three zones, as marked in Fig. 5(a). The difference in the three zones can also be observed from fluctuated profiles of moving average velocities in Fig. 5(a). In Fig. 5(b), the probability density function curves of the tracer moving velocities in the zone descending from $z = 48$ cm to $z = -5$ cm have a peak value of around 4 cm/s and a similar width of the peak as compared to the 90 mm orifice case, indicating a good measurement repeatability at conditions with a narrow orifice opening. The sand mass flow rates calculated based on tracer average velocities in different zones as marked in Fig. 5(a) are presented in Fig. 5(c), which is much higher than that obtained from the accumulation method using a weighing scale, indicating the effect of a narrow orifice on the tracer movement during the measurement, compared to that in Fig. 4(d). The difference of tracer movement in yz plane of the coordinate axes is further illustrated in Fig. 5(d), where the tracers used in tests C#4-1 and C#4-2 travelled from the side next to the Plexiglas wall to the center when approaching the orifice exit. The detailed tracer particle trajectory in the standpipe from tests using different orifice sizes is illustrated in Fig. S4 in the Supporting Information.

A good fit between the tracer-tracking method and the accumulation method was also obtained from Test C#3, during which no orifice was used to regulate the sand flow in the bottom of the standpipe and a quick discharge was obtained. As shown in Fig. 6, the tracer moves from

Fig. 5. Magnetic tracer measurement and sand mass flow in the standpipe with a 41 mm orifice at the bottom exit: (a) C#4-1, C#4-2, tracer position and velocities in z direction, zone 1 ($z = 54$ cm to $z = 48$ cm), zone 2 ($z = 48$ cm to $z = 18$ cm), and zone 3 ($z = 18$ cm to $z = -5$ cm) as marked; (b) probability density function of tracer moving average velocities in z direction, testing zone descending from $z = 48$ cm to $z = -5$ cm; (c) comparison of sand mass flow rates obtained using measured tracer velocities, model correction results, and the accumulation method; (d) tracer position in yz plane in the coordinate axes of the magnetic tracer tracking system, the standpipe center area is marked using the axis (standpipe diameter 123 mm, C#4-1 and C#4-2 used a 41 mm orifice, C#1-1, C#1-2, C#1-3 used a 90 mm orifice, and C#3 had no orifice).

Fig. 6. Magnetic tracer measurement in the vertical standpipe without an orifice at the exit (test C#3).

around $z = 45$ cm to $z = -5$ cm in the coordinate axes within 0.2 s. The calculated sand mass flow rate is around 50 kg/s based on the measured tracer velocity, the sand bulk density, and the cross-section area of the standpipe, which is quite close to that obtained from the sand accumulation method using a weighing scale.

The comparison among cases with three different orifice sizes shows that a small orifice in the bottom of the standpipe can affect the movement of sand and the tracer measurements. This could be attributed to the formation of a non-uniform axial velocity profile and sand flow (v_f), as shown in Fig. 7(a). Consequently, the tracer can be dragged toward the center area of the vertical standpipe where the sand flow has higher velocities, which can be observed from the profiles of test C#4-1 and C#4-2 in Fig. 5(d). Therefore, the magnetic tracer follows the high-velocity sand flow, and the measured velocity is higher than the average velocity across the cross section of the standpipe. However, the adverse effect of the presence of an orifice can be neglected when the orifice size is over 90 mm in this application, equivalent to the ratio of the orifice area opening over 56%. This is due to the relatively uniform velocity distribution across the cross section of the standpipe, as illustrated in Fig. 7(b). In a test without an orifice, as shown in Fig. 7(c), the velocity distribution is uniform across the cross section. The wall effect on solid movement at the boundary layer next to the wall is neglected.

A model was constructed to correct the measurement deviation when using a narrow orifice, as illustrated in Fig. 7(d). It is assumed that the

Fig. 7. Schematic view of the tracer movement in axial and radial directions: (a) tracer travel when using a 41 mm orifice at the exit of the vertical standpipe; (b) tracer movement when using a 90 mm orifice at the exit of the vertical standpipe; (c) tracer movement when using no orifice at the exit of the vertical standpipe; (d) model to calculate the solid mass flow when using a narrow orifice.

sand has a higher moving velocity in the center area, while the sand velocity decreases when approaching the wall. It should be noted that the high velocity area in the upper zone of the sand bed could be wider than that close to the orifice exit, with two velocity fields $v_f(r)$ in different heights illustrated in Fig. 7(a). However, when approaching the orifice exit, the velocity in the center area could be higher, which can be observed from the velocities after $t = 18$ s in Fig. 5(a). Assuming the high velocity area is the same as the orifice opening area, the calculation of the sand mass flow can be expressed as

$$m_S = \int_{r_0}^R v_f(r) \rho_b \cdot 2\pi r dr + v_t \rho_b \cdot \pi r_0^2 \quad (5)$$

where r_0 is the orifice radius and R is the standpipe radius. $v_f(r)$ denotes the sand flow velocity distribution, which highly depends on the size of orifice used in the test. It is assumed that the velocity $v_f(r_0)$ at $r = r_0$ equals the velocity (v_t) measured by the tracer in the test (assuming the tracer is in the high velocity area) and the velocity $v_f(R)$ at $r = R$ is zero. A linear distribution profile between the $r = r_0$ and $r = R$ is assumed for calculation. ρ_b is the bulk density of the sand flow.

The sand mass flow calculated after considering the non-uniform velocity distribution across the standpipe cross-section using the constructed model is shown in Fig. 5(c). The modeling results fit well with that obtained by the accumulation method, indicating the velocity distribution across the standpipe cross section when using a narrow orifice needs to be included for sand mass flow calculation. Although the measurement deviation is observed in tests using a narrow orifice, the constructed model can avoid the constraints of a narrow orifice in the application of the magnetic tracer-tracking method, providing a way to

correctly interpret measurement results.

3.1.3. Effect of tracer size and shape

Fig. 8 shows the effect of tracer sizes on the tracer movement in x , y , and z directions, when using a 41 mm orifice. It can be observed from the curves in Fig. 8(a) that occasionally the positions in x , y , and z directions change with an obvious jump, which might be attributed to the rolling of the spherical tracer on the bed surface during solids discharge. In Fig. 8 (b), where a 7 mm spherical tracer was used, the change of the positions exhibits a much bigger jump at $t = 13.5$ s, indicating that the 7 mm tracer rolls more easily due to its lower particle density compared to the 6 mm spherical tracer used in Fig. 8(a). This finding can be further supported by the result in Fig. 8(c), where the position curve in z direction is relatively straight and the curves in x and y directions fluctuate in a much narrow range compared to that in Fig. 8(a), since the 3×3 mm bare tracer used in Fig. 8(c) is in a cylindrical shape and has a high particle density. Low velocity and high velocity zones can be observed along the tracer position profiles in z direction in Fig. 8(a) and (b), while in Fig. 8(c) the line is relatively linear except at around $t = 21$ s. The tests using different tracers were repeated two to three times and a similar phenomenon can be observed from the repeated tests, as shown in Fig. 8 (d). The effective densities of the tracers used in tests C#5, C#6, and C#7 are shown in Fig. 9(a). The tracer particle shape and density have a significant effect on the tracer movement on the bed surface. It is likely that the cylindrical tracer is more difficult to travel in the radial direction during solids discharge with the descending solids in the standpipe. The bigger the tracer casing is, the more the spherical tracer rolls down with a spiral track.

The moving average of tracer velocities of tests C#5–1, C#6–1, and

Fig. 8. Effect of tracer particle sizes on the tracer position in x, y, and z directions, using a 41 mm orifice (a) C#5-1, 6 mm spherical tracer; (b) C#6-1, 7 mm spherical tracer; (c) C#7-1, bare tracer without plastic casing, 3 × 3 mm cylindrical magnetic tracer; (d) change of tracer position in yz plane in the coordinate axes of the magnetic tracer tracking system in the standpipe.

C#7-1 were calculated, with the corresponding probability density function presented in Fig. 9(b). It can be observed that the peak of the curve of C#6-1 shifts to lower velocities compared to that of C#5-1, however, there is still a long tail on the right side of the curve, which is due to occasional tracer jumps observed from the position curves in z direction in Fig. 8(b). In contrast, the peak of the curve of C#7-1 shifts to higher velocities. Moreover, the profile of C#7-1 has the narrowest peak width. It is interesting to note that C#5-1 has a somewhat larger peak width than C#6-1. The average velocities of tests C#5-1, C#6-1, C#7-1, and C#4-2 and their corresponding standard deviation are further illustrated in Fig. 9(c), where the most significant deviation can be observed from test #6-1 using a 7 mm tracer and while test C#7-1 using a 3 × 3 mm bare tracer without casing shows the minimum deviation among the three tests. C#7-1 also has the lowest average velocity in Fig. 9(c). Therefore, the sinking of the high-density heavier tracer particle in the sand bed cannot be observed. Test C#4 used a 7.5 mm tracer with a 4 × 4 mm cylindrical magnetic core. The tracer used has a particle density of around 2000 kg/m³, which is much smaller than the bare tracer used in test C#7-1 (7600 kg/m³); however, the standard deviation of the moving average velocities in test C#4-2 is even less than that of test C#7-1 using bare magnetic tracer. It is likely that the heavier tracer, due to the larger magnetic inner core, has less deviation in velocity. Even though the total mass of used tracer is larger, the average velocity of C#4-2 still falls in the range same as that of tests using tracers with a 3 × 3 mm magnetic inner core, as shown in Fig. 9(c), indicating that the heavier tracer does not exhibit an obvious sinking in the sand bed. The solid mass flow rate was also compared with the

results obtained from the accumulation method, as shown in Fig. 9(d). It can be observed that all the results calculated based on the magnetic tracer velocity in the whole measurement zone deviate significantly from that measured using accumulation method. However, after a correction using the constructed model in Fig. 7(d) and Equation (5), the discrepancy between the tracer measurement and the accumulation method can be mitigated significantly, as shown in Fig. 9(d). A linear velocity distribution was assumed for the area next to the wall, as shown in Fig. 7(d); however, this can be further improved by determining a more accurate velocity distribution profile across the standpipe cross section, which can also increase the accuracy of the tracer measurement results after model correction.

A comparison of tracer position profiles of tests using different tracers is shown in Fig. 10(a). The initial time in Fig. 10(a) was set starting at z = 40 cm. The deviation of the curve of test C#6-1 from test C#7-1 starts from the very beginning, increases, and lasts for the whole measurement zone. With decreasing the casing size of the tracer from 7 mm to 6 mm (C#5-1), the deviation is much less in the first 5 s but starts increasing after that. Test C#7-1 and C#4-1 have a good fit for most of the measurement zones except the zone after around t = 8 s. It seems that the cylindrical bare tracer (high particle density) and the heavier spherical tracer show a different movement behavior in the magnetic sensing zone compared to other light spherical tracers (used in C#5-1 and C#6-1).

Apart from the trajectory in x, y, and z directions, the tracer rotation status is another important indicator to understand how the tracer interacts with its surrounding solids flow. Fig. 10(b) and (c) shows the

Fig. 9. Effect of tracer particle shape and density on axial velocity measurement: (a) tracer particle density, volume-equivalent spherical diameter for bare magnetic cylindrical tracers; (b) effect of tracer size on probability density function of measured tracer moving average velocities in z direction, testing zone descending from $z = 41 \text{ cm}$ to $z = -5 \text{ cm}$; (c) tracer average velocity and the standard deviation of moving average velocities in the standpipe, the errors bar denotes the standard deviation; (d) comparison of sand mass flow rates measured by tracer-tracking measurement and accumulation methods.

change of theta and phi angles (the definition of the angles is illustrated Fig. 1) compared to the status at the initial point in Fig. 10(a). An obvious change of both theta and phi angles can be observed from test C#6-1 at around $z = 30 \text{ mm}$, corresponding to that where a jump can be observed from the tracer position curve of C#6-1 at $t = 3.8 \text{ s}$ in Fig. 10(a). This provides evidence to show a significant rotation of the tracer experienced during the measurement. The change of theta angles of C#5-1, C#7-1, and C#4-1 deviate each other significantly in the sensing zone below $z = 25 \text{ cm}$ in the coordinate axes while a significant change of phi angle starts when the tracers move to the zone below $z = 10 \text{ cm}$, corresponding to the occurrence of tracer position deviation at $t = 4 \text{ s}$ and $t = 8 \text{ s}$ in Fig. 10(a), respectively. The effect of tracer size on the tracer projection in xy plane is illustrated in Fig. 10(d). The color bar in Fig. 10(d) denotes the time as used in Fig. 10(a). The travel of the tracer in test C#6-1 from the left side to the right side in Fig. 10(d) can be clearly observed at around $t = 4 \text{ s}$, while the travel of tracers in tests of C#4-1, C#5-1, and C#7-1, exhibits a trend of moving toward to the center axis, as discussed above in Fig. 7(a) and (b). The different behaviors of the tracer in test C#6-1, compared to others of C#4-1, C#5-1, and C#7-1, could be attributed to the low tracer particle density, which is even lower than the bulk density of sand flow, as indicated in Fig. 9(a).

The magnetic tracer might segregate in radial and vertical directions. Several factors, including convection [48], gravity and buoyant forces [42], granular temperature (the kinetic energy associated with velocity

variances) [49], and particle concentrations [40], have been shown to play important roles in the segregation process in systems with granular materials differing in density and size. Fan and Hill [40] applied kinetic theory to predict the segregation trend of dense particles in the radial direction of a sheared system in a vertical chute particles dense flow, and reported that the dense particles segregate toward the center (regions of lower shear rates and lower granular temperatures) and the less-dense particles segregate toward the walls (region of higher shear rates). Due to the narrow orifice and the non-uniform velocity distribution, as shown in Fig. 11(a), the sand discharge in the vertical standpipe can be considered as a sheared flow. When the tracer has a lower particle density than the bulk density of the sand flow, there is a tendency for the tracer to migrate toward to the wall, whereas the heavy tracer can move toward the center area of the standpipe. This is consistent with the observed behaviors of the tracers in test of C#6-1, C#4-1, C#5-1, and C#7-1 in Fig. 10(d). It should be noted that the tracer migration in the radial direction does not affect the measurement accuracy in tests using a large orifice, as shown in Fig. 4(d) and Fig. 6. The effect should be considered when using a narrow orifice, together with the constructed model, for sand mass flow rate calculations.

Moreover, the differences among tracers' profiles in Fig. 10(d) can also be attributed to their different segregation in the vertical direction. Based on the effects of static pressure field in water where the Archimedes' principle operate, it is intuitive to expect that light particles move upward while heavy particles move downward [41]. While, in a

Fig. 10. Tracer rotation in the vertical standpipe with a 41 mm orifice: (a) effect of tracer sizes on particle trajectory in z direction, obvious change and deviation among tests marked; (b) effect of tracer sizes on the change of theta angle, obvious change and deviation among tests marked; (c) effect of tracer sizes on the change of phi angle, obvious change and deviation among tests marked; (d) effect of tracer sizes on the tracer projection in xy plane in the coordinate axes of the magnetic tracer tracking system.

solid dense flow system, the segregation can be more complex. Cagnoli and Romano [41] investigated the vertical segregations of 2 cm rock cuboids in particles on a rotating disk to simulate the deposits of dense geophysical flows. They reported the segregation is caused by the agitation gradient in the vertical direction that exists within granular flows. The upward segregation of the rock cuboid is due to that the collision force exerted on the lower surface of the segregating clast is larger in magnitude than that exerted on the upper surface. In Fig. 11(a), due to the differences in velocities and shear rate in the radial direction, the sand particles under the tracer could also move from the wall toward the center areas down a slope, which is similar to an inclined plane flow at an inclination angle [50–52], with a model set-up and schematic trajectory of a tracer illustrated in Fig. 11(b), where it is assumed that the tracer is completely immersed in a granular solid bed with a moving flow along a slope at an angle β (related to sand repose angle and orifice size). A detailed modeling of tracer behaviors in a granular solid flow is out of the scope of this study and saved for the future. For simplicity, only the vertical motion of the tracer relative to the descending sand flow is considered, as expressed as

$$m_t \frac{\partial v_r}{\partial t} = F_b + F_d + m_t g \quad (6)$$

where g is the gravitational acceleration, and m_t is the tracer particle mass,

$$m_t = \frac{\pi \rho_t d_t^3}{6} \quad (7)$$

where d_t is the volume equivalent diameter of the tracer.

v_r is the relative velocity of the tracer to the descending sand flow

$$v_r = v_t - v_f \quad (8)$$

F_d is the viscous drag force

$$F_d = -C_D \eta d_t v_r \quad (9)$$

where C_D is a constant, η is the apparent viscosity.

F_b is the segregation force, consisting of two terms related to pressure gradients and shear gradients along the z direction in the flow [53,54], as expressed below

$$F_b = -\frac{\pi d_t^2}{4} (F \frac{\partial P}{\partial z} + G \frac{\partial \tau}{\partial z}) \quad (10)$$

$\partial P / \partial z$ is pressure gradients, $\partial \tau / \partial z$ is shear-stress gradients, F and G are two empirical functions of the local effective friction and the intruder-to-bed particle size ratio $a = d_t / d_s$ [54]. In this study, the intruder size is the volume equivalent diameter of the tracer.

Assuming a uniform shear flow, F_b can be simplified and well described by a size-ratio-dependent buoyance force [53]. Khakhar et al. [43] analyzed a heavy tracer particle in a medium of light particles and proposed a “buoyancy” mechanism by assuming the heavy tracer particle to be immersed in a continuum of fluid, which was shown to successfully reproduce gravity-driven segregation according to particle density in rotating drums [55].

Fig. 11. Schematic view of the tracer movement in axial direction: (a) vertical segregation of light tracer; (b) model set-up and schematic trajectory of a tracer.

$$F_b = -f\phi\rho_s g \frac{\pi d_t^3}{6} \quad (11)$$

ϕ is the bulk packing fraction, ρ_s is the intrinsic density of the bed particles, f is a function of the ratio $a = d_t/d_s$, d_s is the average size of the sand particles, provided in Fig. 3.

Assuming the tracer is at a steady status, $\partial v_r / \partial t = 0$, and substituting the forces in Equation (7), (9) and (11) to Equation (6), an expression can be obtained in Equation (12).

$$v_r = \frac{(\rho_t - f\phi\rho_s)gd_t^2}{6C_D\eta} \quad (12)$$

f can be calculated via Equation (13) [53].

$$f(a) = [1 - 1.43\exp(-a/0.92)][1 + 3.55\exp(-a/2.94)] \quad (13)$$

For the 7 mm tracer used in test of C#6–1, by inserting values of the 7 mm tracer in Equation (12) gives Equation (14) according to

$$v_r = -\frac{(\rho_t - 1 \cdot \rho_{\text{bulk}})gd_t^2}{6C_D\eta} \quad (14)$$

where $\rho_{\text{bulk}} = \phi\rho_s$ is the bulk density of the sand.

From Equation (14) we can see that when the tracer has a higher density than the bulk density of the fluid medium, the tracer dropped from the top may remain partially immersed in the bed. In contrast, when the tracer density is lower than the fluid medium, since the force exerted on the tracer particle is larger than the tracer's gravity force, the tracer particle might be lifted upward and float on the bed surface, allowing the tracer to travel and roll on the bed surface more easily, as illustrated in Fig. 11 (a). When the tracer density is higher than the fluid medium, the gravity force is higher, the tracer dropped to the bed surface might migrate downward and be immersed into the bed, which might hinder the tracer's free movement in the radial direction.

The change of ϕ angle highly depends on the formation of swirling flow in the presence of a narrow orifice at the bottom of the vertical standpipe. The effect turns out to be more obvious when approaching the orifice, as observed in Fig. 10(c). However, when the tracer is

immersed deeply into the bed, the tracer's movement during solids discharge can be different. The effect of bed depth above the tracer on the tracer's movement is presented in detail in the following section.

It should be noted that the relative distance in the bed that the tracer travels in axial and radial directions in the dense flow is much less compared to the sand movement in the axial direction due to a high sand flow velocity. The segregation could significantly affect the measurement accuracy only when there is a non-uniform velocity distribution across the standpipe cross-section. When the tracer segregates to the wall where the velocity of sand particles is lower due to narrow orifice, a lower tracer moving velocity can be obtained, yielding a lower sand mass flow rate in the standpipe. Both the position of the tracer in the radial direction and the non-uniform velocity distribution therefore should be considered for calculation and correction. However, when the velocity distribution across the standpipe cross-section is uniform, the velocity measured by the tracer after segregation toward the wall could still yield representative measurement results.

3.1.4. Effect of the tracer position in the bed

Tracers immersed in the solid particles can behave differently from those just floated on the bed surface since their movement in the radial direction, depending on the depth, is constrained by the gravity and forces that exerted on the tracer particle. Fig. 12(a) shows the probability density function of moving average velocities of tracers that were immersed with different depths in the bed in the standpipe with a 41 mm orifice: the 1st, 2nd, and 3rd tracers have a depth of 1.9 m, 0.95 m, 0 m, respectively. The 1st tracer has a peak value of around 3 cm/s. While the 2nd tracer shows a similar peak value but its peak shifts slightly to higher velocities, indicating a higher probability of high moving velocities. A more obvious shifting to the high velocity side in Fig. 12(a) can be observed from the 3rd tracer. The average velocities of the three tracers in test C#8–1, together with that from repeated tests C#8–2 and C#8–3, are plotted versus the initial bed height above the tracer and shown in Fig. 12(b). A significant fluctuation of the moving average velocities can be observed in Fig. 12(b). A low average velocity value can be observed from the 2nd tracer in test C#8–3, which could be attributed to the non-uniform velocity distribution of sand flow and the

Fig. 12. Axial velocities of tracers with different depths in the standpipe with a 41 mm orifice: (a) probability density function of three tracers' moving average velocities in z direction, C#8-1; (b) effect of in-bed depth of the tracer on the average velocity and the fluctuation of the moving average velocities measurement; (c) solid mass flow calculated based on single tracer's average velocity in the sensing zone; (d) solid mass flow calculated based on the distance and travel time (Equation (3)) between two neighbouring tracers.

position of the 2nd tracer significantly deviated from the axial center of the standpipe. The position in xy plane of used tracers in tests C#8-1 and C#8-3 are shown in Fig. S5. As shown in Fig. S5(a), in C#8-3, the 2nd tracer remained in the zone near the standpipe wall, where the sand moving velocity could be relatively lower compared to that in the zone where the 1st and 3rd tracers were located. It indicates that, when using a narrow orifice, the measurement results of the tracer can be affected by the tracer position in the radial direction. In test C#8-1, the three tracers moved toward and finally fell in the center area in xy plane, as shown in Fig. S5(b), which allows meaningful comparisons among the three tracers. There seems to be a trend that the average velocity of the moving-average velocities decreases with the increase of bed height above the tracer, as observed in Fig. 12(a) and (b). It might be attributed to the change of the sand funnel flow formed in the center and the stagnant zone formed above the orifice near the wall during the test. Since the bed height was continuously decreasing during the solids discharge, the force exerted on sand particles in the zone above the circular orifice decreased accordingly. The size and height of the stagnant zone above the circular orifice near the standpipe wall could increase. As shown in Fig. S6, the high velocity zone starts at $z = 12.5$ cm for the 1st tracer, while it occurs at a higher position in z direction at around $z = 22.5$ cm and $z = 28$ cm for the 2nd and 3rd tracers, respectively, inferring the increase of the height of the stagnant zone. Consequently, the occurrence of the transition of the tracer into the high velocity funnel flow shifts to a higher position in z direction along the standpipe height.

Fig. 12(c) shows the corresponding solid mass flow results and the comparison with the results obtained using the accumulation method. The solid mass flow measured by the accumulation method is very stable at around 0.4 kg/s with a minor variation in most of test period and exhibits an obvious increase after $t = 110$ s, indicating the flow disturbance caused by the narrow orifice size when approaching the exit. Although the results obtained by the tracer-tracking method vary significantly and are over 50 % above that measured by the accumulation method, it seems that the tracer-tracking measurement can still capture the increasing trend of solid mass flow with the elapsed time. Interestingly, the solid mass flow calculated based on the solid moving velocity in Equation (3) between neighboring tracers fits very well with that measured by the accumulation method, as shown in Fig. 12(d). The discrepancy between the two methods in the period between $t = 70$ s and $t = 120$ s could be attributed to the poor measurement accuracy for tracers floating on the bed surface when approaching the narrow orifice exit.

Fig. 13 shows the measurement results of tracers in different depths in the standpipe with a 90 mm orifice at the bottom exit. The 2nd tracer has a high probability density of high moving average velocities over 10 cm/s among the three tracers in Fig. 13(a), while the peak of the 3rd tracer shifts to the left, inferring that no obvious trend of the effect of tracer in-bed depth can be observed. The average velocity, together with the fluctuation, is plotted versus the bed height above the tracer in Fig. 13(b). The velocity only increases slightly with increasing the bed height. However, the velocity fluctuation for the tracer (1st tracer) with

Fig. 13. Axial velocities of tracers with different depths in the standpipe with a 90 mm orifice: (a) probability density function of three tracers' moving average velocities in z direction; (b) effect of in-bed depth above the tracer on the average velocity and fluctuation of the moving average velocities; (c) solid mass flow calculated based on single tracer's average velocity in the sensing zone; (d) solid mass flow based on the distance and travel time (Equation (3)) between two neighboring tracers.

an in-bed depth of 1.95 m is much less than that (3rd tracer) floated on the bed surface in test C#9. After converting to the mass flow rate versus the elapsed time in Fig. 13(c), a good fit between the tracer-tracking and accumulation methods can be observed. The mass flow rate measured by the accumulation method decreases slightly at around $t = 10$ s in Fig. 13(c), which seems to be able to be captured by the tracer-tracking measurement. A better fit between the two methods can be achieved in Fig. 13(d), where the calculation of the solid mass flow rate was based on the distance and travel time (Equation (3)) between two neighboring tracers.

3.2. Measurement of solids movement in the standpipe & inclined pipe

As mentioned above, the tracer-tracking measurement could be disturbed when the tracer is approaching the narrow orifice at the exit. In this section, the effect of adding an inclined pipe between the exit and the sensing zone is presented and discussed. The bed density in the standpipe & inclined pipe was also regulated via mixing biomass and sand particles at different proportions to simulate the bed in the presence of entrained low-density biochar particles.

3.2.1. Effect of the orifice size

Fig. 14(a) shows the position and velocities of two tracers with different depths in the vertical standpipe connected with an inclined pipe and a 41 mm orifice. A good linear fitting can be obtained for the

two position curves in z direction. The curves have a slope rate almost identical to each other. The corresponding velocities also show profiles with quite similar probability density function in Fig. 14(b). The solid mass flows calculated by individual tracers' average velocities and the travel (Equation (3)) between two neighboring tracers fit well with that measured by the accumulation method, as shown in Fig. 14(c), indicating that the disturbance caused by the narrow orifice (41 mm) observed in Fig. 5(c) can be avoided after using an inclined pipe. It is worthy to note that the solid mass flow increases after $t = 90$ s, which corresponds to the solids bed surface descending in the inclined pipe, indicating the existence of flow disturbance when the shallow bed surface level approaching the orifice exit. According to the curve measured by the accumulation method in Fig. 14(c), there might be a waving behavior of solids discharge from the orifice exit. A good fit between the tracer-tracking and accumulation methods can also be observed from tests C#11 and C#12, which have an opening of 90 mm and 123 mm, respectively, at the exit of the inclined pipe, as shown in Fig. 14(d).

Fig. 15 shows the effect of the existence of inclined pipe on the tracer average velocities of tests using different orifice sizes at the exit. In tests without an inclined pipe, with increasing the orifice size, the tracer velocity increases first at a rate nearly proportional to the increase of orifice's cross section area; however, it is followed by a significant increase when no orifice is used. It infers that the formation of flow disturbances resulting from the utilization of an orifice has a significant effect on the solids movement in the vertical pipe. With respect to tests

Fig. 14. Axial velocities of tracers with different depths in the standpipe with an inclined pipe (a) probability density function, C#10, 41 mm orifice; (b) effect of bed height above the tracer on the velocity measurement, 41 mm orifice; (c) solid mass flow based on single tracer movement, 41 mm orifice; (d) Solid mass flow based on the distance and travel time (Equation (3)) between two neighboring tracers, C#11 (90 mm orifice), C#12 (fully open, no orifice).

Fig. 15. Effect of orifice size on the tracer velocity in the standpipe without and with an inclined pipe (without an inclined pipe: C#1, C#3, C#4; with an inclined pipe: C#10, C#11, C#12).

with an inclined pipe, while the tracer velocity at conditions with a 41 mm orifice size is lower compared to that with the same orifice size but no inclined pipe, the tracer velocity could significantly increase when increasing the orifice size to 90 mm. The tracer velocity finally levels off

with further increasing the orifice size to the maximum size identical to the standpipe size. This is interesting since it seems that the hindering effect observed from tests with an orifice directly at the bottom of the vertical standpipe can be effectively mitigated by the adoption of an inclined pipe between the orifice and the standpipe, which could be attributed to the change of the solids flow pattern at the area near the orifice exit. As shown in Fig. S7(a), in tests using a vertical standpipe, a symmetric stress-free surface (SFS) can form in the vicinity of the orifice, above which the particles are in contact with one another and below which the particles are in free fall and accelerate freely under gravity [56]. The solids pour continuously through the stress-free surface. When using an inclined pipe, an asymmetric stress-free surface could form instead due to asymmetric forces exerted on the particles near the stress-free surface, as illustrated in Fig. S7(b), which might facilitate solids discharge through the orifice. Moreover, it should be noted that the solids flow could also be hindered by the inclined pipe, depending on its angle to the horizontal [57]. The two factors might compete in the measurement tests. When a narrow orifice of 41 mm was used, the solids flow could be mainly controlled by the orifice size and the angle of the inclined pipe. However, with increasing the orifice size to 90 mm, the change of stress-free surface and flow pattern in the vicinity near the orifice turns out to be a dominant role. Although the solids movement is hard to measure directly, interactions between the tracer and solids particles can also provide insight into the solids discharge behaviors under different conditions to understand this counterintuitive phenomenon.

Fig. 16 shows the change of theta and phi angles of tracers in tests

Fig. 16. Effect of orifice size on tracer rotation: (a) change of theta angle, C#10 (41 mm orifice), C#11 (90 mm orifice); (b) change of theta angle, C#12 (no orifice); (c) change of phi angle; (d) tracer projection in xy plane with the elapsed time.

using different orifice sizes. In Fig. 16(a), the 1st tracer of test C#10 was immersed in the bed and exhibited a profile with a much larger angle change and a more frequent oscillation, compared to that of the tracer (2nd tracer) floated on the bed surface. The frequent oscillation might be caused by the intermittent pulse flow of solids particles. Consequently, the sand flow velocity might vary with fluctuation, as illustrated in Fig. 17(a), which can affect the tracer movement due to the differences in density, weight and inert force. Assuming both the tracer and sand have the same velocity during the steady status, where,

$v_r = v_t - v_f = 0$, there is no drag force exerted on the tracer at this time. When the sand flow velocity slows down due to the intermittent pulse phenomenon, the relative velocity $v_r = v_t - v_f > 0$, as shown in Fig. 17(b), an upward drag force can be exerted on the bottom of the tracer when moving downward, rotating the tracer a little bit; the tracer velocity will then be slowed down and follow the sand flow. However, when the sand flow velocity increases, the relative velocity $v_r = v_t - v_f < 0$, and a force in an opposite direction could act on the tracer and turn its rotation backward, as shown in Fig. 17(c). The change frequency of the relative velocity between the tracer and sand particles flow can result in the change of drag force exerted on the tracer, in consequence, causing the tracer rotation in the axial and radial directions, as illustrated in Fig. 17(d) and (e). An analysis of the tracer angle can provide insights into the sand flow pulsing behaviors. The rotation cannot be observed from test C#11, which used a 90 mm orifice at the end of the inclined pipe, indicating that much less interactions between solid particles and tracer. It implies that the solids particles moved down smoothly when 90 mm orifice was used and both the solids

and the tracer had a similar velocity during discharge. In test C#12 without an orifice at the end of the inclined pipe, a significant rotation can be observed in Fig. 16(b), indicating that the solids flow has a high moving down velocity dragging the tracer to rotate. There is much less rotation in the radial direction, except the 2nd tracer in test C#10, which might roll around on the bed surface during the discharge, as shown in Fig. 16(c). The tracers' projection in xy plane (perpendicular to z axis) is illustrated in Fig. 16(d). A trend of tracer movement towards the center axis during solids discharge can be observed from the 1st and 2nd tracers in test C#11.

3.2.2. Effect of solids density

Since the solids materials in the standpipe of typical fluidized bed gasifiers and combustors comprise of a mixture of both bed materials and carbonaceous particles, the solids bulk density in the standpipe can vary significantly with different proportions of carbonaceous particles. Fig. 18 shows the effect of solids bulk density on the tracer velocity in the standpipe with an inclined pipe. With a 90 mm orifice at the exit of the inclined pipe, as shown in Fig. 18(a), test C#13 has the lowest bed height but exhibits the longest time for a complete discharge among all the cases. Test C#15 also has a longer discharge time than C#11. Moreover, it seems that the curves, especially from tests with a low bed density, consist of several stages with different slope rates along the solid mass change profile in Fig. 18(a) for test C#13. Similar results can be observed in Fig. 18(b), where no orifice was used at the exit of the inclined pipe. Test C#19 has a similar bed height as test C#16, while its discharge time is much longer. Different stages along the curves can also be determined. The measurement results using the magnetic tracer-

Fig. 17. Schematic view of the tracer rotation in axial and radial directions: (a) change of sand flow velocity due to pulsing behaviors; (b) contact force upward exerted on the tracer when $v_t > v_f$; (c) contact force downward exerted on the tracer when $v_t < v_f$; (d) tracer rotation in axial direction; (e) tracer rotation in radial direction.

tracking method are illustrated in Fig. 18(c) and (d). The initial position of the tracer in test C#13 is at around $z = 60$ cm. With the elapsed time, the tracer descends with the solids flow and the curve shows a good linearity within the first 3 s. However, a significant waving can be observed from the curve between $t = 3$ s and $t = 8$ s. Tests C#15 and C#17 used two tracers, with the 1st one immersed deep in the bed and the 2nd on the bed surface. The 1st tracer disappeared quickly after passing through the sensing zone. Subsequently, the 2nd tracer was detected. The curves of tests C#15 and C#17 exhibit a much better linearity at the 2nd stage compared to that of test C#13. Moreover, the curve of test C#17 shows a steeper slope than that of C#15, which might be attributed to the higher bed density of test C#17. However, the waving along the curves of the 2nd tracer in tests C#17 and C#13 can still be observed. In tests without an orifice, the curves in Fig. 18(d) exhibit a much smoother profile compared to that in Fig. 18(c), indicating that the waving and oscillation observed in Fig. 18(c) could be mainly caused by the utilization of the orifice at the exit of the inclined pipe. It is interesting to note that the slope rate of the curves can change with the elapsed time and there could be different stages along the curves in Fig. 18(d).

Fig. 19(a) shows the effect of bed density on the tracer velocity. In tests with 90 mm orifice, the average velocities at the 1st and 2nd stages (Fig. 18(c)) were used. Moreover, for tests using two tracers, the velocity was also calculated based on the distance and travel time (Equation (3)) between two neighboring tracers. A monotonous trend of the tracer velocity with increasing the bed density can be observed until the bed density reaches 1250 kg/m^3 . However, in tests without any orifice, the tracer velocity first increases to around 60 cm/s with increasing the bed density (solids bulk density) from 480 kg/m^3 to 800 kg/m^3 and then levels off in a wide range of bed density between 800 kg/m^3 and 1300 kg/m^3 , followed by a decrease to around 30 cm/s at the bed density of

1780 kg/m^3 .

Considering the differences in bed density, the mass flow is further presented in Fig. 19(b) to show the effect of bed density on the solid mass flow in the standpipe. More details are presented in Table 3, where the mass change period corresponding to the calculated mass flow rate is also given. A monotonous trend can also be observed from tests using 90 mm orifice. The mass flow rate was also calculated based on total accumulation mass and time for each test. A good fit between the magnetic tracer-tracking and accumulation methods can be obtained at both stage 1 and stage 2. Among all the methods, the results at stage 2 calculated by both magnetic tracer-tracking and accumulation methods also fit well with that calculated by the total loaded solids divided by the total discharge time, indicating the measurement results at stage 2 could be a representative of the whole test. Different from what has been observed for tests without orifice in Fig. 19(a), a level-off stage cannot be observed from the solid mass flow curves obtained by both tracer-tracking and accumulation methods in Fig. 19(b). In tests without orifice at the exit of the inclined pipe, the mass flow reaches the maximum value of around 8 kg/s at the density of 1250 kg/m^3 and then decreases to around 6.6 kg/s at the density of 1780 kg/m^3 . The tracer tracking results at stage 2 fit well with that obtained from the accumulation method, as shown in Fig. 19(b) and Table 3. However, a significant deviation between the two methods can be observed at Stage 1 in Table 3. The main reason is that at the very beginning of solids discharge the high mass flow in tests without orifice has a sudden and high impact force on the collected bucket and weighing scale, which causes mass readings higher than the actual mass of solids collected. However, at stage 2 both results from the magnetic tracer-tracking method and accumulation method fit well with that calculated by the total loaded solids divided by the total discharge time, which is validated in a much wider range of 30–90 % of mass change in the whole

Fig. 18. Effect of bed density on the tracer velocity in the vertical standpipe and inclined pipe (a) solids mass change, 90 mm orifice size; (b) solids mass change, no orifice; (c) tracer position in z direction in the standpipe, 90 mm orifice size; (d) tracer position in z direction in the standpipe, no orifice.

test, demonstrating the applicability and accuracy of the magnetic tracer-tracking method in tests with a high solids mass flow rate. Care should be taken when interpreting the results obtained by the accumulation method in the whole test period because of the impact on the weighing scale readings in the very beginning of solids discharge.

In test C#12, the mass flow measured by the tracer-tracking method is slightly larger than that obtained using the accumulation method, as shown in Fig. 19(b). While in test C#18, the mass flow measured by the tracer is slightly lower than that obtained using the accumulation methods. This could be attributed to the waving behaviors of the solids discharge flow determined during the tests. An obvious change of the tracer moving velocity can be observed from the tracer position profile in test C#12, as shown in Fig. S8 in the Supporting Information, indicating the waving behaviors during the solids discharge. The selected zone between $t = 1$ s and $t = 2.3$ s might have a velocity slightly higher than the average velocity in the whole test period, resulting in the deviation of the mass flow rates obtained using different methods. In test C#18, the trajectories of the 2nd tracer between $t = 2$ s and $t = 2.5$ s in Fig. 18(d) were used for calculating the sand mass flow, while the profile at the corresponding time (between $t = 2$ s and $t = 2.5$ s) in Fig. 18(b) exhibits a slow mass change than that before $t = 2$ s. In test C#16, the second tracer was not detected due to a signal issue. The tracer profile obtained in the early stage of solids discharge, as shown in Fig. 18(d), was used, which could be the reason for the obvious deviation of the mass flows obtained using the tracer-tracking and accumulation methods in test C#16.

The sand flow velocity in a standpipe with an orifice highly depends

on the standpipe geometry, orifice size, and the solids physical properties[58]. Therefore, the solids fluid velocity can be expressed as

$$v_f = c \left(\frac{gD_0}{\tan\alpha} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (15)$$

where c is a constant related to the angle of the inclined pipe, D_0 is the diameter of orifice opening, and α is the angle of internal friction of the mixture.

The mass flow rate can be obtained via Equation (16)

$$m_f = \pi R^2 \cdot \varphi \rho_s \cdot c \left(\frac{gD_0}{\tan\alpha} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (16)$$

where $\varphi \rho_s$ is the bulk density of the mixture.

The effect of bed density on the moving velocity in Fig. 19(a) could be attributed to the change of the internal friction angle of the solids mixture. The angle could change with the fraction of added carbonaceous particles and particles sizes of each component in the mixture [59,60]. A non-monotonous trend of the angle with the varied proportions of components in the mixture could occur [60]. Moreover, the angle might be also affected by the compactness of the mixture [61], which mostly depends on the orifice opening and solids moving down velocity in the standpipe of this study since no external forces were loaded. There could be a maximum allowable fluid velocity, around 0.6 m/s, as determined in Fig. 19(a). A further increase of the velocity might need aeration gas flow. However, a detailed analysis is out of the scope

Fig. 19. Effect of solids bulk density:(a) tracer velocity in z direction; (b) solid mass flow.

of this study.

The magnetic tracer-tracking technique is considered applicable to all other fluidized bed systems that adopt a standpipe to transport and return solids, including circulating fluidized beds, twin fluidized-beds, and fluidized-bed catalytic cracking (FCC) units. The standpipe is generally combined with a loop seal, which has been widely used in thousands of CFB systems to transport and circulate solids particles. Also, it can be connected to an inclined pipe, as investigated in this study. A single magnetic tracer can be injected from the top of the

standpipe, following the moving packed-bed flow in the standpipe and yielding real-time velocities for monitoring the performance of the fluidized bed system and calculating the solids mass flow or circulation rate in a full-loop fluidized bed system. The technique can be used in cold flow fluidized beds under both atmospheric and pressurized conditions for the measurement of solids circulation rate and hydrodynamics in the standpipe. The high temperature in the standpipe is the main constraint limiting the application of the technique in hot fluidized bed systems operated at a high temperature above 550 °C (e.g. 800–1000 °C in boilers and gasifiers); however, this could be addressed via selecting suitable magnetic materials with a high working temperature and cooling sand particles in the standpipe to keep the working temperature in the standpipe below the temperature limit of the selected magnetic material.

4. Conclusion

The magnetic tracer-tracking system has been applied in measuring solids discharge in a fluidized bed standpipe. The magnetic tracer-tracking method shows a good measurement accuracy for the measurement in a vertical standpipe when compared to that measured by the descending and accumulation methods. However, using a small orifice at the exit of the vertical standpipe can affect the tracer measurements and the effect can be neglected when the area ratio of the orifice size opening to the standpipe size reaches 56 %. The tracer measurement, when using a narrow orifice, can significantly overestimate the solid discharge rate. However, the measurement results were corrected using a constructed mathematical model and good measurement accuracy was achieved for tests using a narrow orifice. Interestingly the solid mass flow calculated based on the distance and the travel time between two neighboring tracers fits very well with that obtained by the accumulation method.

The tracer shape and density have an obvious effect on the tracer movement on the bed surface. The bigger the tracer casing is, the easier the spherical tracer rolls down with a spiral track when descending with the solids flow. It is likely that the cylindrical tracer is more difficult to deviate in the radial direction. Although no clear trend of tracer velocity versus increasing the in-bed depth of tracer immersed in the solids can be observed, the fluctuation of moving average velocities for the tracer with a deep in-bed depth is much less than that floated on the bed surface, indicating the interactions between the tracer and solids particles.

The measurement accuracy of the magnetic tracer-tracking method, when using a narrow orifice at the exit, as stated above, can also be improved significantly when there is an inclined pipe between the vertical standpipe and the narrow orifice. Moreover, the tracer velocity in tests with a 90 mm orifice also increases significantly after adding the

Table 3

Comparison of results obtained from tracer-tracking and accumulation methods.

	Stage 1				Stage 2				Whole test	
	Tracer-tracking		Accumulation		Tracer-tracking		Accumulation		Discharge time	Accumulation
	Mass change	Mass flow	Mass change	Mass flow	Mass change	Mass flow	Mass change	Mass flow	Mass flow	Mass flow
	%	kg/s	%	kg/s	%	kg/s	%	kg/s	kg/s	kg/s
Orifice 90 mm										
#13	0–20	1.15	2–14	1.17	20–28	0.34	28–35	0.39	0.52	0.53
#15	0–9	2.11	0–13	2.10	20–42	1.49	20–43	1.43	1.08	1.17
#17	1–8	4.47	0–11	4.15	18–35	2.18	15–28	1.92	1.54	1.63
#11	5–17	5.79	10–34	5.86					5.04	5.93
Without orifice										
#19					26–44	1.70	30–60	1.67	1.83	2.13
#14	0–30	5.52	0–30	20.30			33–90	5.67	5.78	7.1
#16	0–11	6.55	0–30	14.89			30–60	7.68	7.94	10.25
#18	0–8	9.03	0–20	30.42	15–30	8.11 ^a	18–85	8.38	8.40	9.51
#12					12–28	6.55	15–100	6.08	6.28	6.98

^a used in Fig. 19b.

inclined pipe. It seems that the hindering effect observed from tests with an orifice directly at the exit of a vertical standpipe can be effectively mitigated due to the existence of an inclined pipe between the orifice and the standpipe.

An analysis of the tracer angle can provide insights into the interaction between tracer and solids particles and the sand flow pulsing behaviors. Forces exerted on the tracer particles to rotate can change with the solids discharge flow velocity, when using different orifice sizes in a configuration with both vertical standpipe and inclined pipe to regulate the solids flow. A frequent oscillation of tracer angle change observed from the test with a narrow orifice might be caused by the intermittent pulse flow of solid particles. Very little change of angles can be observed from the tracer when using a 90 mm orifice, while the tracer in the test without an orifice rotated significantly, since the solid flow has a high moving down velocity dragging the tracer to rotate.

The bed density has an obvious effect on the tracer velocity and solids mass flow in the standpipe. A monotonous trend of the tracer velocity with increasing the bed density can be observed. In tests without any orifice, the tracer velocity first increases to around 60 cm/s with increasing the bed density from 480 kg/m³ to 800 kg/m³ and then levels off in a wide range of bed density between 800 kg/m³ and 1250 kg/m³, followed by a decrease to around 30 cm/s at the bed density of 1780 kg/m³. However, a level-off stage cannot be observed from the solid mass flow curves. The effect of adding carbonaceous particles on solids flow velocity could be related to the change of internal friction angle of the mixture.

The waving and pulsing phenomenon during solids discharge can be observed from the tracer trajectory profiles. Therefore, the magnetic tracer-tracking method can not only predict the solid discharge flow rate but also behaviors that cannot be determined using conventional descending and accumulation methods.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Chunguang Zhou: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Christian Jonasson:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Software, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Marcus Gullberg:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Project administration, Investigation. **Fredrik Ahrentorp:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Investigation. **Christer Johansson:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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References

- [1] S. Bhusarapu, P. Fongarland, M.H. Al-Dahhan, M.P. Duduković, Measurement of overall solids mass flux in a gas–solid circulating fluidized bed, *Powder Technol.* 148 (2004) 158–171, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2004.09.007>.
- [2] P. Basu, Chapter 8 - Design of Biomass Gasifiers, in: P. Basu (Ed.), *Biomass Gasification, Pyrolysis Torrefaction*, Second Ed., Academic Press, Boston, 2013, pp. 249–313, <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-396488-5.00008-3>.
- [3] X. Liu, M. Zhang, S. Zhang, Y. Ding, Z. Huang, T. Zhou, H. Yang, G. Yue, Measuring technologies for CFB solid circulation rate: a review and future perspectives, *Energies* 15 (2022) 417, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en15020417>.
- [4] E.R. Monazam, R. Panday, L.J. Shadle, Estimate of solid flow rate from pressure measurement in circulating fluidized bed, *Powder Technol.* 203 (2010) 91–97, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2010.03.030>.
- [5] G. Patience, J. Chaouki, B. Grandjean, Solids flow metering from pressure drop measurement in circulating fluidized beds, *Powder Technol.* 61 (1990) 95–99, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0032-5910\(90\)80070-F](https://doi.org/10.1016/0032-5910(90)80070-F).
- [6] D.C. Gufo-Pérez, F. Dietrich, J.N. Ferreira Cala, T. Pröll, H. Hofbauer, Estimation of solids circulation rate through magnetic tracer tests, *Powder Technol.* 316 (2017) 650–657, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2017.04.062>.
- [7] A. Miller, D. Gidaspow, Dense, vertical gas-solid flow in a pipe, *AIChE J.* 38 (1992) 1801–1815, <https://doi.org/10.1002/aic.690381111>.
- [8] B. Herb, S. Dou, K. Tuzla, J.C. Chen, Solid mass fluxes in circulating fluidized beds, *Powder Technol.* 70 (1992) 197–205, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0032-5910\(92\)80054-Z](https://doi.org/10.1016/0032-5910(92)80054-Z).
- [9] M. Laura Mastellone, U. Arena, The effect of particle size and density on solids distribution along the riser of a circulating fluidized bed, *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 54 (1999) 5383–5391, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0009-2509\(99\)00272-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0009-2509(99)00272-9).
- [10] W. Zhang, F. Johnsson, B. Leckner, Momentum probe and sampling probe for measurement of particle flow properties in CFB boilers, *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 52 (1997) 497–509, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0009-2509\(96\)00423-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0009-2509(96)00423-X).
- [11] J.J. Burkell, J.R. Grace, J. Zhao, C.J. Lim, Measurement of solids circulation rates in circulating fluidized beds, in: P. Basu, J.F. Large (Eds.), *Circ. Fluid. Bed Technol.*, Pergamon, 1988: pp. 501–509. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-036225-0.50054-X>.
- [12] E.-U. Hartge, D. Rensner, J. Werther, Solids concentration and velocity patterns in circulating fluidized beds, in: P. Basu, J.F. Large (Eds.), *Circ. Fluid. Bed Technol.*, Pergamon, 1988: pp. 165–180. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-036225-0.50020-4>.
- [13] S. Sun, X. Lu, S. Zhou, Q. Wang, J. Chen, J. Li, X. Xie, C. Liu, Investigation on heat exchange feasibility of internal solids circulation for an ultra-supercritical CFB boiler, *Powder Technol.* 339 (2018) 223–231, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2018.06.048>.
- [14] C. Wang, J. Zhu, S. Barghi, C. Li, Axial and radial development of solids holdup in a high flux/density gas–solids circulating fluidized bed, *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 108 (2014) 233–243, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ces.2013.12.042>.
- [15] A.J. Jaworski, T. Dyakowski, Application of electrical capacitance tomography for measurement of gas–solids flow characteristics in a pneumatic conveying system, *Meas. Sci. Technol.* 12 (2001) 1109, <https://doi.org/10.1088/0957-0233/12/8/317>.
- [16] S. Malcus, G. Chaplin, T. Pugsley, The hydrodynamics of the high-density bottom zone in a CFB riser analyzed by means of electrical capacitance tomography (ECT), *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 55 (2000) 4129–4138, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0009-2509\(00\)00083-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0009-2509(00)00083-X).
- [17] S. Bhusarapu, M.H. Al-Dahhan, M.P. Duduković, Solids flow mapping in a gas–solid riser: Mean holdup and velocity fields, *Powder Technol.* 163 (2006) 98–123, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2006.01.013>.
- [18] W. Wu, D.C. Gufo-Pérez, M. Bonmann, F. Johnsson, L. Duan, D. Pallarès, Radar-based measurement of solids back-mixing in the freeboard of a circulating fluidized bed, *Chem. Eng. J.* 488 (2024) 151150, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2024.151150>.
- [19] S.W. Kim, S.D. Kim, Effects of particle properties on solids recycle in loop-seal of a circulating fluidized bed, *Powder Technol.* 124 (2002) 76–84, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0032-5910\(01\)00472-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0032-5910(01)00472-7).
- [20] R. Kobylecki, M. Horio, A simple solid mass flow meter for circulating fluidized beds, *J. Chem. Eng. Jpn.* 35 (2002) 456–467, <https://doi.org/10.1252/cej.35.456>.
- [21] B.J. Harris, C.E. Davies, J.F. Davidson, The slot flow meter: a new device for continuous solids flow measurement, *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 52 (1997) 4637–4648, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0009-2509\(97\)00305-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0009-2509(97)00305-9).
- [22] A. Kreuzeder, C. Pfeifer, H. Hofbauer, Fluid-dynamic investigations in a scaled cold model for a dual fluidized bed biomass steam gasification process: solid flux measurements and optimization of the cyclone, *Int. J. Chem. React. Eng.* 5 (2007), <https://doi.org/10.2202/1542-6580.1394>.
- [23] W. Wu, A.L. Gerhart, Z. Chen, P.A. Dellenback, P.K. Agarwal, A device for measuring solids flowrate in a circulating fluidized bed, *Powder Technol.* 120 (2001) 151–158, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0032-5910\(01\)00274-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0032-5910(01)00274-1).
- [24] H. Masuda, K. Iinoya, Electrification of particles by impact on inclined metal plates, *AIChE J.* 24 (1978) 950–956, <https://doi.org/10.1002/aic.690240603>.
- [25] P.M. Heertjes, J. Verloop, R. Willems, The measurement of local mass flow rates and particle velocities in fluid–solids flow, *Powder Technol.* 4 (1970) 38–40, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0032-5910\(70\)80006-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0032-5910(70)80006-7).
- [26] J. Liu, B. Huan, Turbine meter for the measurement of bulk solids flowrate, *Powder Technol.* 82 (1995) 145–151, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0032-5910\(95\)92535-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0032-5910(95)92535-X).
- [27] J.C. Ludlow, L.O. Lawson, L.J. Shadle, M. Syamlal, Development of a spiral device for measuring the solids flow in a circulating fluidized bed, *Circ. Fluid. Bed Technol.* VII (2002) 513.

- [28] L.J. Shadle, J.C. Ludlow, J.S. Mei, C. Guenther, Circulating fluid-bed technology for advanced power systems, National Energy Technology Lab, Pittsburgh, PA, and Morgantown, WV; Fluent, 2001 accessed January 9, 2024.
- [29] J.C. Ludlow, E.R. Monazam, L.J. Shadle, Improvement of continuous solid circulation rate measurement in a cold flow circulating fluidized bed, *Powder Technol.* 182 (2008) 379–387, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2007.06.031>.
- [30] J. Hu, D. Liu, C. Liang, J. Ma, X. Chen, T. Zhang, Solids flow characteristics and circulation rate in an internally circulating fluidized bed, *Particuology* 54 (2021) 69–77, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.partic.2020.02.009>.
- [31] M. Kuramoto, D. Kunii, T. Furusawa, Flow of dense fluidized particles through an opening in a circulation system, *Powder Technol.* 47 (1986) 141–149, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0032-5910\(86\)80110-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0032-5910(86)80110-3).
- [32] A.V. Mitrofanov, E.A. Shuina, I.A. Tikhomirova, K. Tannous, Computational and experimental study of drying of disperse materials in a circulating fluidized bed, *Fibre Chem.* 51 (2019) 293–296, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10692-020-10099-5>.
- [33] M.H. Rahman, X.T. Bi, J.R. Grace, C.J. Lim, Measurement of solids circulation rate in a high-temperature dual fluidized bed pilot plant, *Powder Technol.* 316 (2017) 658–669, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2017.01.073>.
- [34] S. Roy, A. Kemoun, M. Al-Dahhan, M.P. Dudukovic, A method for estimating the solids circulation rate in a closed-loop circulating fluidized bed, *Powder Technol.* 121 (2001) 213–222, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0032-5910\(01\)00353-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0032-5910(01)00353-9).
- [35] D.C. Gufo-Pérez, T. Pröll, J. Wassermann, H. Hofbauer, Design of an inductance measurement system for determination of particle residence time in a dual circulating fluidized bed cold flow model, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 52 (2013) 10732–10740, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ie400211h>.
- [36] X. Zhu, P. Dong, Q. Tu, Z. Zhu, W. Yang, H. Wang, Investigation of gas-solids flow characteristics in a pressurized circulating fluidized bed by experiment and simulation, *Powder Technol.* 366 (2020) 420–433, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2020.02.047>.
- [37] E. Sette, D. Pallarès, F. Johnsson, F. Ahrentorp, A. Ericsson, C. Johansson, Magnetic tracer-particle tracking in a fluid dynamically down-scaled bubbling fluidized bed, *Fuel Process. Technol.* 138 (2015) 368–377, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuproc.2015.06.016>.
- [38] A. Köhler, D. Pallarès, F. Johnsson, Magnetic tracking of a fuel particle in a fluid-dynamically down-scaled fluidized bed, *Fuel Process. Technol.* 162 (2017) 147–156, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuproc.2017.03.018>.
- [39] A. Köhler, A. Rasch, D. Pallarès, F. Johnsson, Experimental characterization of axial fuel mixing in fluidized beds by magnetic particle tracking, *Powder Technol.* 316 (2017) 492–499, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2016.12.093>.
- [40] Y. Fan, K.M. Hill, Shear-induced segregation of particles by material density, *Phys. Rev. E* 92 (2015) 022211, <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevE.92.022211>.
- [41] B. Cagnoli, G.P. Romano, Vertical segregations in flows of angular rock fragments: Experimental simulations of the agitation gradient within dense geophysical flows, *J. Volcanol. Geotherm. Res.* 265 (2013) 52–59, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvolgeores.2013.08.017>.
- [42] N. Shishodia, C.R. Wassgren, Particle segregation in vibrofluidized beds due to buoyant forces, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 87 (2001) 084302, <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.87.084302>.
- [43] D.V. Khakhar, J.J. McCarthy, J.M. Ottino, Radial segregation of granular mixtures in rotating cylinders, *Phys. Fluids* 9 (1997) 3600–3614, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.869498>.
- [44] N.K. Mitani, H.-G. Matuttis, T. Kadono, Density and size segregation in deposits of pyroclastic flow, *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 31 (2004), <https://doi.org/10.1029/2004GL020117>.
- [45] Custom Rare Earth Magnets and Magnetic Assemblies | Stanford Magnets, (n.d.). <https://www.stanfordmagnets.com/> (accessed June 8, 2024).
- [46] Souwest Magnetech: Custom Magnets Supplier In China, Custom Magnetic Material And Products, NINGBO SOUWEST MAGNETECH Dev. COLTD (n.d.). <https://www.magnetsw.com/> (accessed June 10, 2024).
- [47] E.E. Corporation, Electron Energy Corporation | Rare Earth Magnetic Solutions Worldwide, (n.d.). <https://www.electronenergy.com> (accessed June 10, 2024).
- [48] C.H. Tai, S.S. Hsiau, C.A. Kruelle, Density segregation in a vertically vibrated granular bed, *Powder Technol.* 204 (2010) 255–262, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2010.08.010>.
- [49] J.T. Jenkins, D.K. Yoon, Segregation in binary mixtures under gravity, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 88 (2002) 194301, <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.88.194301>.
- [50] A.V. Yennemadi, D.V. Khakhar, Drag, lift, and buoyancy forces on a single large particle in dense granular flows, *Phys. Rev. Fluids* 8 (2023) 074301, <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevFluids.8.074301>.
- [51] N. Wang, H. Lu, J. Xu, X. Guo, H. Liu, Granular flows of binary mixtures down an inclined channel, *Int. J. Multiph. Flow* 120 (2019) 103097, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmultiphaseflow.2019.103097>.
- [52] L. Jing, J.M. Ottino, R.M. Lueptow, P.B. Umbanhowar, A unified description of gravity- and kinematics-induced segregation forces in dense granular flows, *J. Fluid Mech.* 925 (2021) A29, <https://doi.org/10.1017/jfm.2021.688>.
- [53] Drag force in granular shear flows: regimes, scaling laws and implications for segregation | Journal of Fluid Mechanics | Cambridge Core, (n.d.). <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/journal-of-fluid-mechanics/article/abs/drag-force-in-granular-shear-flows-regimes-scaling-laws-and-implications-for-segregation/C3FDA5E6EF105A7474941543C07FD8C7> (accessed June 15, 2024).
- [54] F. Guillard, Y. Forterre, O. Pouliquen, Scaling laws for segregation forces in dense sheared granular flows, *J. Fluid Mech.* 807 (2016) R1, <https://doi.org/10.1017/jfm.2016.605>.
- [55] Segregation-driven organization in chaotic granular flows | PNAS, (n.d.). <https://www.pnas.org/doi/full/10.1073/pnas.96.21.11701> (accessed June 15, 2024).
- [56] J.-Y. Zhang, V. Rudolph, Flow instability in non-fluidized standpipe flow, *Powder Technol.* 97 (1998) 109–117, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0032-5910\(97\)03395-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0032-5910(97)03395-0).
- [57] D.P. O’Dea, V. Rudolph, Y.O. Chong, Gas—solids flow through the bottom restriction of an inclined standpipe, *Powder Technol.* 62 (1990) 291–297, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0032-5910\(90\)80116-G](https://doi.org/10.1016/0032-5910(90)80116-G).
- [58] L.S. Leung, P.J. Jones, T.M. Knowlton, An analysis of moving-bed flow of solids down standpipes and side valves, *Powder Technol.* 19 (1978) 7–15, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0032-5910\(78\)80069-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0032-5910(78)80069-2).
- [59] M. Stasiak, M. Molenda, M. Bańda, E. Gondek, Mechanical properties of sawdust and woodchips, *Fuel* 159 (2015) 900–908, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2015.07.044>.
- [60] M. Benjelloun, R. Bouferra, H. Ibouh, F. Jamin, I. Benessalah, A. Arab, Mechanical behavior of sand mixed with rubber aggregates, *Appl. Sci.* 11 (2021) 11395, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app112311395>.
- [61] F. Daghistani, A. Baghbani, H. Abuel Naga, R.S. Faradonbeh, Internal friction angle of cohesionless binary mixture sand-granular rubber using experimental study and machine learning, *Geosciences* 13 (2023) 197, <https://doi.org/10.3390/geosciences13070197>.